

AGRICULTURAL GROWTH AND POLITICAL REGIMES

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Abstract

Given the nexus between polity and economy, it was expected that political regimes definitely have impact on agricultural growth. But empirical results were lacking in this regard. This led to current study being conducted on finding differences in trend and growth of real value of agricultural production and real value added in agricultural sector for 85 countries of the world. The study used secondary data. The data was aggregated based on polity type and then linear trend analysis was used. The study found that autocracies had statistically higher growth of real value of agricultural production and real value added in agricultural sector over the period of 1992 to 2018 than democracies. The study suggested democracies to adopt growth promoting policies which exists in autocracies.

Key words: Democracy, Autocracy, Agriculture, GDP, Growth

Introduction

The type of government or political regimes matters for an economy because the government makes policy decisions and frames rules and regulations which affect the economic variables. This interconnectedness between polity and economics has led many research studies directed towards finding effect of autocracy and democracy, two major forms of government, on economic growth (Mukand & Rodrik, 2015; Rodrik, n.d.; Rodrik & Wacziarg, 2005), protection from international trade (Beghin & Kherallah, 1991; Olper, 2001) and human rights' violation (Mulligan et al., 2004). The agriculture sector being a primary sector of the economy isn't immune from decisions of the government. The government very often intervenes in the markets and sets prices for many of the staple commodities. In some countries government act as single largest buyer of the agricultural commodities. Thus, it is pertinent that government has acted as big-daddy in the economy. Therefore, it is necessary that type of government would have affected type of crops being grown around the country, value of crops being grown and value-added in the agricultural sector (Pieters et al., 2014; Swinnen et al., 2000).

The existing literature on political regimes assets that the democratic governments have short sighted policies which hamper growth and development. In contrast, autocratic governments act like big capitalist and run country as a corporation, making heavy capital investments in economy for long-run growth and development (Iqbal et al., 2008; Przeworski & Limongi, 1993). Thus, apriori, it is expected that democratic governments lead to less growth in long-run. However, conflicting views exists regarding economic growth. Regarding agricultural growth, there was no literature. Therefore, it was decided to conduct study to find trend and growth of real value added in agricultural sector and real gross value of production for agricultural sector for autocracy and democracy.

Materials and Methods

The study is based on secondary data collected from FAO Statistics (FAOSTAT, 2022) on area harvested, gross value of production (at constant 2014-16 prices in US \$) and value added in agricultural sector (at constant 2015 prices in US \$) from 1992 to 2018. The data on polity score was obtained from Polity Project website (Marshall & Gurr, Ted Robert, 2020). Based on availability of data, 85 countries were selected. Countries with polity score of more than zero were classified as democracy and autocracy otherwise. Country-wise data was aggregated for each year for each political regime. The aggregate data was converted into per hectare values using gross area harvested before further statistical analysis. Thus, for 27 years data there were

54 observations (27 each for autocracy and democracy) To estimate growth rate and trend of real value of agricultural production and value added in agricultural sector, linear trend analysis was used. The coefficient of time period was trend coefficient. To jointly estimate two separate equations, dummy variable for regime (1 for democracy and 0 for autocracy) was used and interaction between regime dummy and time variable was also incorporated. After this inclusion, intercept served as autocracy benchmark and coefficient of time period served as trend coefficient for autocracy. To find intercept for democracy, intercept must be added with coefficient of regime dummy. To find trend coefficient for democracy, trend coefficient of autocracy must be added with coefficient for regime dummy and time interaction. The trend coefficient divided by average value of dependent variable for respective regime provided the simple growth rate. Assuming that autocorrelation and heteroscedasticity are common econometric problems faced in regression, Heteroscedasticity and Autocorrelation Consistent (HAC) standard errors (Newey & West, 1987) were used for hypothesis testing.

Results and Discussion

From Figure 1 and 2, it can be observed that autocracies had consistently higher real value of agricultural production and value added in agricultural sector as compared to democracies over the 27 years period. This shows that autocracies were engaged in production of high value enterprises compared to democracies. The high value added per hectare also indicates that the autocratic regimes are more efficient in converting the resources into value. This proves the hypothesis that autocracies are congenial for growth. The empirical proof is provided in Table 1. From Table 1, it can be observed that coefficient of regime dummy was negative for both regressions, meaning that average value of dependent variable for democratic regime was significantly less than that of autocratic regime. The coefficient of regime and time interaction was also negative meaning that the growth rate of democratic regime was significantly less than that of autocratic regime. The simple growth rate of real value added per hectare was 5.18 percent per annum for autocratic regime as compared to 1.37 percent per annum for democratic regime. Similarly, the simple growth rate of real value of production per hectare was 4.09 percent per annum for autocratic regime as compared to 1.51 percent per annum for democratic regime. The R square (coefficient of determination) value was .99 for both regressions, meaning that linear trend was very good fit for both the dependent variables. The p-value of F-statistic was nearly zero (or very low) meaning that all the estimated regression coefficients were statistically significantly different from zero.

Figure 1. Real value of agricultural production per hectare over time for different political regimes

Figure 2. Real value added in agricultural sector (per hectare) over time for different political regimes

Table 1. Robust estimates of trend of real value added and real value of production per hectare from agricultural Sector from 1992-2018

Particulars	Real value added per hectare	Real value of production per hectare
(Intercept)	490.18 ***	577.94 ***
Regime Democracy Dummy	-115.08 *	-26.51
Year (Time)	45.69 ***	39.60 ***
Regime Democracy Dummy *Year	-33.62 ***	-24.97 ***
Mean value of dependent variable (US \$)	882.88	968.16
Simple Growth rate for Autocratic regime (%)	5.18	4.09
Simple Growth rate for democratic regime (%)	1.37	1.51
Number of observations	54.00	54.00
R square	0.99	0.99
Loglikelihood	-284.08	-261.66
Akaike Information Criteria	578.16	533.32
F-statistics	1104.49	1494.23
p-value	0.00	0.00

Significance Codes: *** $p < 0.00$; ** $p < 0.01$; * $p < 0.05$.

Conclusion

The study found that autocracies are congenial for growth of agriculture than democracies. The study recommends the democracies to adopt growth promoting policies from autocracies. The outcome of this study shall be helpful to policy makers in adjusting the existing policy design to suit and accommodate the needs for more wholistic and pro-growth policies.

Future Scope

Given the outcome of this study, the future researchers may further evaluate the policy design of each autocratic and democratic nations to find policy differences and better suggest policy aspects related to agriculture.

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Conflict of Interest

There is no conflict of interest involved in this study for the authors.

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